

SUSTAINABILITY EFFECTS OF GREEN HRM PRACTICES: CHALLENGES AND IMPACTS ON ENVIRONMENTAL ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE

NARAYANI BHATT

Research Scholar, Department of Management, Indus University, Ahmedabad, Gujarat.

Dr. DHARMIL PATEL

Assistant Professor, Department of Management, Indus University, Ahmedabad, Gujarat.

Abstract

Green human resource management is one of the most critical components of a forward-thinking, eco-friendly company in today's society. The majority of academics hold the opinion that in order to implement green human resource management techniques, personnel must be empowered and environmentally conscious. The goal of the current study was to ascertain how green human resource strategies affected employee engagement and environmental sustainability in Bahrain's industrial companies. The originality of the current study was noted to be the mediating role of employee engagement. The information was gathered from officials, staff members, and clerical workers at Bahraini manufacturing companies that strive for green practices. Employee engagement serves as a mediator between green human resource practices and environmental sustainability, according to the study, which also revealed a favorable relationship between the two.

Keywords: Green HRM, Practices, Environment, Sustainability, Human Resource Management.

1. INTRODUCTION

Growing global environmental concerns and rising international standards now require companies to adopt and integrate proven technologies into their operations. To comply with rules and regulations, many companies adopt compliance strategies for their environmental or green management projects. However, external factors such as popular boycotts, coercive tastes and new consumer demand are influencing the company's strategy. Environmental compatibility is gaining increasing importance among management scientists. Research studies addressing how human resource management systems can help organizations work towards environmental sustainability despite their importance to management, employees, customers and other stakeholders. is surprisingly low. As a result, there is a growing demand for incorporating environmental management into human resource management (HRM) research practice, especially green HRM.

Although many studies highlight the benefits of environmental management systems (EMS) in organizations, the depth of research still depends on how well EMS is implemented. Due to the competitive advantages that a green HRM system offers, companies are increasingly supporting it. A key observation is that green companies have a greater impact on environmental performance. The introduction of a green HRM system represents an attempt to achieve a wide range of outcomes that are actually very important for companies. The main

purpose of this study is to explore how environmentally conscious HRM practices impact organizations and how these practices affect the environment through business operations.

Environmental considerations become more important to companies as they interact with both customers and employees. Employee pressure to solve environmental problems often comes from the employees themselves. Therefore, the idea of “green talent management” is the most well-known phenomenon for forward-thinking companies. GHRM is a green program aimed at increasing employee engagement, reducing costs and improving work efficiency. HRM scientists are currently working on projects to help companies implement better environmental practices as interest in this area grows. However, the impact of the GHRM system as a whole on environmental outcomes (waste reduction) and business performance has received less attention. As an organization will eventually adopt new strategies and policies to leverage them, it is important to focus on outcomes that support the organization's GHRM practices.

Sustainability in a company's environmental, social, and financial performance is now considered as a significant societal duty, especially in activities focused at protecting the environment. How well GHRM practices are accepted affects superior firm performance. Activities under green human resource management (GHRM) include green hiring and selection, green preparation and improvement, green performance management, and green pay and benefits. Green human resource management is being used by businesses more and more as a fundamental framework for implementing green tactics that enhance environmental performance and yield long-lasting outcomes. The environmentally conscious corporate culture that GHRM practices promote was found to be a clear hindrance to the link between GHRM practices and environmental performance.

1.1. Green HRM practices

The fact that employees in any firm can increase environmental sustainability by adopting pro-environmental behaviors is now widely acknowledged. The grave scenario where the climate is irrevocably changing, environmental damage, and resource shortages are driving an increase in pro-environmental efforts within organizations. Nowadays, environmental protection is a growing trend on a global scale. The concern of every society forces many organizations to establish environmental protection strategies. When a company uses GHR practices, it means it has adopted new environmental sustainability approaches, procedures, policies, and plans. The HR department is in charge of educating and training the workforce on environmental sustainability. Combining HR policies and practices offers a number of benefits, including increased employee engagement, cost savings, and performance effectiveness.

1.2. Environmental sustainability (ES)

Employees must be dedicated, trained, and given license to take pro-environmental acts in order for the environment to be sustained. These elements act as mediators. According to the World Commission on Environment and Development, sustainable development involves addressing present needs without compromising those of future generations. Sustainable ecosystems improved environmental quality by preventing environmental destruction and depletion. It consists of three stages, the first of which is when the business modifies its

organizational structure in response to environmental laws and regulations. In the second stage, the group focused its efforts on environmental protection by reducing pollutants and taking other suitable measures. In the third phase, environmental sustainability is guaranteed by voluntary proactive activities.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

M. W. Shaikh (2014) examined the worth of green HRM in the twenty-first 100 years. He examines the upsides of green HRM. It helps with garbage the board, contamination decrease, and boss marking and picture. Green practices should be incorporated into organizations by HR administrators. The method involved with practicing environmental safety incorporates directing natural reviews, utilizing eco-accommodating things, and utilizing eco-accommodating advancements. HR is fit for changing over from regular bundling materials like plastic sacks and metal jars to harmless to the ecosystem bundling materials.

A few green practices incorporate e-business, paperless workplaces, e-learning, and waste administration. The utilization of non-harmful, reused, and climate agreeable structure materials, insignificant site and scene unsettling influence, indoor air quality for wellbeing and security, the utilization of energy-proficient and harmless to the ecosystem gear, sustainable power sources, and the utilization of endlessly water reusing are a portion of the qualities of green structures that were covered by the scientist. As per a survey directed by M/S Buck experts, 76% of respondents utilized video conferencing and voyaged less, 54% of firms included ecological administration, and 60% took on work out schedules in the working environment. Green HR rehearses have been executed by undertakings in India, and green mindfulness is developing rapidly.

As indicated by the mental social hypothesis of green HRM, Zoogah David B. (2011) analyzed the elements of green HR conduct. The start and upkeep of Green HRM conduct depend on the assumptions, encoding, cooperation, objectives, values, and self-guideline of the supervisors. Thought is given to the conduct and mental social data handling hypotheses. The reaction and safeguard move made by HR chiefs are made sense of in the article.

Sumantha Dutta (2012) researched Green HRM as a corporate key drive to present reasonable practices in the business. The mentality and conduct of representatives toward the climate relies upon both their expert and individual lives. The practices portrayed by the creator monitor energy and paper.

In this audit article by Jacob Cherian and Cheerful Jacob (2012), the specialist investigated 19 articles and arrived at the resolution that utilizing green human resource the executives increments representative assurance. Furthermore, they noticed that a solid framework for dealing with the climate increments efficiency, raises public insight, draws in better laborers, further develops maintainability, and improves generally speaking execution.

Representatives in this sort of association are driven and effectively keen on natural exercises. Green human resource the board helps with the advancement and acquisition of eco-accommodating products, the decrease of waste, and expanded consumer loyalty.

Dr. Apoorva Trivedi (2015) sums up the meaning of Green HRM to eliminate modern contamination. The enlistment and choice interaction, direction, execution evaluation, preparing and improvement, remuneration or pay the board, professional workplace citizenship, and so on are a few functional limits where HR can change over the HR administrations in a green way. The scientist exhorted a couple of exercises, including reusing, water and power productivity, paperless workplaces, cleaning drives, and yearly energy review overviews. Expanded use of innovation as we go toward digitalization can help with the safeguarding of the regular world.

The fundamental focal point of the exploration article by Shoeb Ahmad (2015) was on the association's shifted Green HRM rehearses and the two critical parts of information capital conservation and harmless to the ecosystem HR rehearses. A part of corporate social obligation is the green HR program. A portion of the drives HR directors can take incorporate green structure, paperless workplaces, energy saving, reusing, and waste disposal. Greening must now be integrated into HR drives. The cutting edge HR chief's obligations incorporate teaching staff individuals and motivating youth to focus on a sound balance between fun and serious activities to help harmless to the ecosystem organizations.

3. CHALLENGES OF GREEN HRM IN THE ORGANIZATION

The task of establishing the strategies intended to produce environmentally friendly planned representatives falls to the HR section of any group. Throughout the process of employing green human resource management, the HR division faces a number of difficulties. The association's successful Green practices and values encounter particular obstacles. Every employee acts in accordance with their own distinct discernment, demeanor, and accepts.

- The most key test is to establish the crucial awareness of the climate among associations. People at all phases of life need to be instilled with a green mindset, and this demand is expanding. The climate management framework shouldn't be used only in one place or only "as and when needed."
- The increase of green consciousness among employees and the training of the representatives to embrace a green balance between enjoyable and important activities are additional critical tests that the associations are focusing on in this cycle. The group must educate its members about the issue and encourage the adoption of environmentally friendly practices.
- Finding personnel who have a green aptitude is a really difficult task. A significant HR concern is finding innovative and creative individuals through green enlistment.
- It is ludicrous to demand that all employees complete the tasks marked in green.
- HR staff members are under strain since they must assign and select employees while also conducting Green HRM training.
- Look for chances to adjust to a new setting.

- It is predicted that tools like funding and sizable worker groups would be used to spread knowledge about the environment and offer training. payments to those who called in exchange for assistance with planning, giving presentations, and other tasks.
- No organization association has a structural base that is sturdy enough to handle the new, innovative modifications that are climate-friendly.
- The hesitation and reserve of the employees present a serious challenge. Some employees believe it is not their responsibility to protect the environment. They didn't have to initiate the implementation of sustainability. The initial arrangement fee for green practices reduces the association's earnings and advantages. For instance, introducing a nearby planet group on the rooftop would involve a substantial establishment expense.

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Figure 1: Proposed Structure

This study was quantitative and cross-sectional in nature. Data were collected from a manufacturing company in Bahrain striving for environmentally friendly practices from the company's employees, including officers, employees and clerks. Data were collected from a sample of the 200 respondents.

4.1. Research design

The research is informal in style. The goal of the study is to determine how Environmental Sustainability and Green HR functions (an independent variable) interact.

4.2. Data collecting method and questioner

to conduct the empirical research into the connections between environmental sustainability and the Green HR functions as outlined by the aforementioned theoretical model. The questionnaire used a 5-point Likert scale, with responses ranging from "strongly agree" to "strongly disagree."

Sample and sampling method

The proportionate stratified random sampling approach will be used in the study to choose the sample from the population. By identifying different strata within a study population that can

anticipate varying parameters, stratified random sampling can then assign a particular proportion to each stratum and choose samples appropriately. The use of this stratified random sampling technique will reduce sampling bias since it gives every component of a given population an equal chance to be sampled.

4.3. Hypothesis of the Study

In light of the prior debate, the analysis gives the following hypotheses.

H1: Employee Engagement Mediates the Connection Between Sustainability and Green Hiring

H2: Employee Engagement Mediates Green T&D and Sustainability Relationships

H3: Employee Engagement Mediates Green Performance and Sustainability Relationship

5. DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

5.1. Reliability analysis

Table 1: Reliability Assessment

S. no	Construct	Cronbach's Alpha
1	EE	.729
2	ES	.707
3	GHI	.698
4	GP	.714
5	GTD	.728

Figure 2: Visualization of the Reliability Analysis

5.2. Demographic analysis

The demographics of each person are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Demographic statistics

Demographics	Frequency	Percent
Gender		
Male	129	64.5%
Female	71	35.5%
Age Group		
25 – 35	129	64.5%
35-45	68	34%
45 and above	3	2.5%
Income Range		
20,000 to 45,000	97	48.5%
45,000 to 70,000	73	36.5%
70,000 and more	30	15%

Figure 3: An illustrated representation of respondents' demographic data

There were 200 responders in all, of which 64.5% were men and 35.5% were women. 66.5% of respondents were in the age range of 25 to 35, 34% were in the 35 to 45 age range, and the final 2.5% were over the age of 45. 48.5% of respondents reported monthly incomes between \$20,000 and \$45,000. 36.5 percent of people have monthly incomes between \$45,000 and \$70,000, and 15% have incomes over \$70,000 (all income numbers are in Pakistani rupees).

5.3. Descriptive analysis

To investigate the mean values of each construct with deviation, descriptive analysis is used. All factors' average scores are at a suitable level with allowable variation (see table 3). By comparing the values of skewness and kurtosis, which are within the recommended range, or 1, the data's normalcy was determined.

Table 3: Descriptive research

Variables	N	Mean	SD	MIN	MAX	Skewness	Kurtosis
EE	200	6.26	.848	1.52	5	.174	.344
ES	200	6.40	.821	1.82	5	.174	.344
GHI	200	6.27	.883	1.42	5	.174	.344
GP	200	6.26	.989	0.42	5	.174	.344
GTD	200	6.24	.938	1.22	5	.174	.344

The current section of the study provides an example of analysis using the measurement model and bootstrapping approach with SMART-PLS. Measurement model shown in Table 4 contains average variance extract, composite reliability, and Cronbach's alpha.

Table 4: Model for Measurement

	Alpha	CR	AVE
EE	0.814	0.879	0.587
ES	0.967	0.983	0.881
GHI	0.969	0.981	0.846
GP	0.924	0.953	0.794
GTD	0.893	0.930	0.688

Figure 4: Visualization of the measurement model

The factual upsides of the estimation model that meet the prerequisites to be supported and keep on being higher than the limit are displayed in the above table.

Table 5: Disparate Validity

	EE	ES	GHI	GP	GTD
EE	0.774				
ES	0.525	0.949			
GHI	0.535	0.739	0.930		
GP	0.460	0.445	0.470	0.901	
GTD	0.324	0.314	0.366	0.475	0.838

The aforementioned table satisfies the requirements for discriminant validity, and the measuring scales are valid and reliable as a result of Tables 4 and 5.

5.4. Structural Equation Modeling (SEM)

Table 6: Facilitating Theory

	Beta	t-values	p-values
GHI -> ES	0.216	3.800	0.002
GP -> ES	0.142	2.762	0.008
GTD -> ES	0.053	0.808	0.454

Figure 5: An illustration of the mediating hypothesis

The H1 and H3 hypotheses were supported, while H2 was statistically rejected, as seen in the aforementioned Table 5, which also illustrates the mediating influence of employee engagement. These findings showed that green human resource practices have a stronger connection to environmental sustainability if people participate in the workplace more effectively.

6. DISCUSSION

It has been found that associations are putting an assortment of green HRM systems to attempt to support maintainability. Notwithstanding, a more serious exertion should be taken to incorporate them, illuminate the labor force about them, urge adherence to such green drives among all partners, and reasonably reward the people who do. Also, it is essential to integrate the green HRM strategy into other HRM activities, for example, recruiting and terminating, preparing and improvement, overseeing execution and compensation, and empowering representative contribution in green HR drives. The concentrate likewise recommends that by underlining waste administration, reusing, keeping up with wellbeing and security guidelines, carrying out gaining from preparing modules, and advancing a harmless to the ecosystem hierarchical culture, representative contribution and cooperation would assume a vital part in advancing hierarchical supportability. By doing this, organizations could in a roundabout way upgrade their image picture and establish a workplace that is more secure, cleaner, and all the more harmless to the ecosystem for both their partners and their representatives.

Bosses and experts can decide the benefit of binds representative commitment with cooperation in ecological administration projects to progress authoritative manageability, with an accentuation on squander the board reusing, and creating green items. Managers can embrace Green HRM practices and arrangements to secure and work on the wellbeing, wellbeing, and prosperity of their labor force with the guide of associations and representatives. The review centers around how HR is associated with maintainability and green drive drives. As per the study, HR is engaged with rousing staff to complete Green HR drives. It encourages worker spirit and dedication toward the drawn out suitability of the organization, which has likewise helped with recruiting and holding staff. With the contribution of workers, the executives, and partners, the fate of green HRM turns out to be more confident soon when associations can reduce their expenses and increment their productivity through it. Taking everything into account, there hasn't been a lot of exploration done regarding this matter. Scholastics can contribute by directing more examination regarding this matter.

7. CONCLUSION

Using GHRM empowers organizations to cut costs while apportioning more assets to speculations that benefit the climate. Bosses who recruit staff fully intent on further developing ecological results have seen an improvement in consumer loyalty and execution. Organizations can prevail in their hierarchical way towards ecological supportability in the event that they can connect practices and human resource aspects with natural administration goals.

The principal objective of the ongoing review is to determine what green human resource rehearses mean for worker commitment and, thus, how they benefit ecological manageability. The review's discoveries showed that green HR rehearses significantly affect representative commitment, and that worker commitment valuably affects ecological maintainability. The organizations should carry out green procedures and run worker preparing projects to assist with staffing individuals embrace techniques that help feasible causes.

The review explores how supportive of natural way of behaving and ecological supportability collaborate with green execution the board and examination, green enrollment and determination, green award and remuneration, and green preparation and advancement. The outcomes have been separated utilizing essential information. To evaluate the association between reasonable ecological exercises and green natural practices, underlying condition demonstrating was utilized in the review. Investigated is the "Supportive of Ecological Way of behaving" that fills in as a middle person between harmless to the ecosystem activities and natural manageability. The results of the green exhibition the board evaluation show that it significantly affects the natural supportability. As per the discoveries, further developing the utilize assessments during natural administration well affects the maintainability of the climate.

References

- 1) Ahmad, S. (2015). Green human resource management: Policies and practices. *Cogent business & management*, 2(1), 1030817.
- 2) AlZgool, M. (2019). Nexus between green HRM and green management towards fostering green values. *Management Science Letters*, 9(12), 2073-2082.
- 3) Arulrajah, A.A.; Opatha, H.H.D.N.P., (2016). Analytical and Theoretical Perspectives on Green Human Resource Management: A Simplified Underpinning. *Int. Bus. Res.*, 9(12): 153-164 (12 pages).
- 4) Ashraf, F.; Ashraf, I.; Anam, W., (2015). Green HR for businesses. *Int. J. Acad. Res. Bus. Soc. Sci.*, 5(8): 149- 156 (8 pages). Boselic, P.; Paauwe, J.; Jansen, P., (2001). Human resource management and performance: lessons from the Netherlands. *Hum. Resour. Manage., J.*, 12(7): 1107-1125 (19 pages).
- 5) Chaudhary, R., (2019). Green human resource management in Indian automobile industry. *J. Global Respons.*, 10(2): 161–175 (15 pages).
- 6) Cheema, S.; Javed, F., (2017). The effects of corporate social responsibility toward green human resource management: The mediating role of sustainable environment. *Cogent Bus. Manage.*, 22 (10 pages).
- 7) Dr. Apoorva Trivedi, *International Journal of Business Quantitative Economics and Applied Management Research*, Volume 2, Issue 2, 2015, 34- 43
- 8) Gill Mandip, (2012), *Green HRM: People Management Commitment to Environmental Sustainability*, *Research Journal of Recent Sciences*, Vol. 1.
- 9) Grabara, J. K. (2017). The another point of view on sustainable management. *QualityAccess to Success*, 18, 344-349.
- 10) Jabbour, C. J. C., Santos, F. C. A., Nagano, M. S. (2010), Contributions of HRM throughout the stages of environmental management: methodological triangulation applied to companies in Brazil, *International Journal of Human Resource Management*, Vol. 21 No. 7, pp. 1049- 1089
- 11) Jacob Cherian & Jolly Jacob, *International Journal of Business and Management*; Vol. 7, No. 21; 2012, 25-33.
- 12) Panzabekova, A., Satybaldin, A., Alibekova, G. & Abilka, N. (2019). Human capital for sustainable development: a comparative analysis of regions of the Republic of Kazakhstan. *OP Conf. Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, 317, 012013.
- 13) Renwick, D. W., Redman, T., & Maguire, S. (2013). Green human resource management: A review and research agenda. *International Journal of Management Reviews*, 15(1), 1- 14.

- 14) Rothenberg, S., (2003), Knowledge Content and Worker Participation in Environmental Management, *Journal of Management Studies*, pp. 17883-1802.
- 15) Shaikh, M. W. (2014). Green HRM, A Requirement of 21st Century. *Abhinva Journal of Research in Commerce and Managemant*, 122-127.
- 16) Shantz, A., Arevshatian, L., Alfes, K., & Bailey, C. (2016). The effect of HRM attributions on emotional exhaustion and the mediating roles of job involvement and work overload. *Human Resource Management Journal*, 26(2), 172-191
- 17) Suhaimi Sudin, (2011). Strategic Green HRM: A proposed model that supports Corporate Environmental Citizenship, *International Conference on Sociality and Economics Development*, Vol. 10.
- 18) Sumanta Dutta, *International Journal of Business Economics and Management Research*, Volume 2, Issue 2, 2012, 143-148
- 19) Wagner, M. (2007). Integration of environmental management with other managerial functions of the firm. Empirical effects on drivers of economic performance *Long Range Planning*, Vol.40 No. 6, pp. 611-628.
- 20) Zoogah, David B., *Ecoston*, The Open Access Publication Server of the ZBW, Information Centre of Economics, 2011